

Research Paper

Application of microalgae in cauliflower fertilisation

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ABSTRACT

In a circular bioeconomy, balancing inorganic fertilisers and microalgae supplementation is important for ensuring sustainable agriculture. This study aimed to evaluate the fertilising effects of live microalgae (mostly *Chlorella vulgaris* and a mixture of *Chlorophyceae* and *Trebouxiophyceae*) on cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* L. subsp. *botrytis*) plant morphology, yield, and quality of cauliflower heads. Microalgae fertilisation effects were analysed by employing an experimental factorial design with two factors: inorganic fertiliser and microalgae, each at high and low dosage levels, and the results revealed higher plant height, wider stem diameter, and lower stem slenderness in high-dose combinations than those in other combinations. In addition, an increase in nitrate, calcium, potassium, and sodium content was observed in the sap of cauliflower leaves in high-dose combinations compared to those in low-dose combinations. The high-dose combination also increased the yield, number of commercial heads, weight of the heads, and number of curds per head of cauliflower. Overall, the study demonstrates that increasing the dose of inorganic fertilisers and microalgae significantly increases nutrient concentration in the sap, which translates into a larger plant, an increase in the number of leaves and yield, and an improvement in the quality of cauliflower heads. These findings underscore the necessity for further research to ascertain the optimal combination of inorganic fertilisers and microalgae to maximise crop yield and cauliflower head quality.

1. Introduction

Cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* L. subsp. *botrytis*) is a crucifer that is consumed and cultivated worldwide under different climatic conditions (Singh and Kalia, 2021). Cauliflower “curds” [the edible portion of the head excluding the butt and leaves attached to the cover (USDA, 2017)] are highly nutritious because of the presence of antioxidant compounds such as glucosinolates, vitamins, phenolic compounds, and carotenoids exerting beneficial health effects (Miceli et al., 2018; Picchi et al., 2020).

Modern agriculture confronts challenges for a sustainable increase in production to meet the demands of the growing global population (Zhang et al., 2021), which has intensified the use of fertilisers (Mitra, 2017). However, the rising costs of chemical fertiliser production and concerns about carbon footprint pose significant constraints. Therefore, exploring suitable alternatives is necessary (Bhalamurugan et al., 2018). The current demand for biofertilisers and biostimulants to improve crop

yield and quality, together with the need to reduce the global carbon footprint and protect the environment, is driving worldwide adoption of agricultural fertilisers of biological origin.

Microalgae are amenable to diverse applications and offer biotechnological solutions (Dagnaisser et al., 2022; Rupawalla et al., 2022). Microalgal extracts are byproducts with potential benefits for modern agriculture; they facilitate enhanced nutrient absorption, increased crop efficiency, nutrient retention, improved physiological status, and biopesticidal properties against pathogens (Bello et al., 2021; Fernández et al., 2021). They also play a crucial role as nitrogen fixers and nutrient-rich resources, which makes them valuable for biofertiliser production (Solovchenko et al., 2016; Chatterjee et al., 2017; Santos and Pires, 2018). Moreover, microalgae promote beneficial microbial interactions, stimulating soil microbe growth and improving overall soil fertility and crop production (Leloup et al., 2013; Ferreira et al., 2021; Álvarez et al., 2021; Mutum et al., 2022; Song et al., 2022). For instance,

Abbreviations: DAT, days after transplantation; EC, electrical conductivity; LSD, least significant difference; SAR, sodium absorption ratio; USDA, United States Department of Agriculture; RH, relative humidity; ET₀, reference evapotranspiration.

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Cyanobacteria inoculation in soil enhances horticultural crop quality, such as increased sugar and carotenoid content in tomatoes (Coppens et al., 2016). *Chlorella* spp., a green alga, has attracted significant attention for its ability to remove nitrogen, phosphorus, and other metals (Dyhrman, 2016). Furthermore, the cost-effectiveness and environmental friendliness of microalgae compared to traditional fertilisers contribute to their demand for enhancing agricultural production while minimising adverse environmental impacts (Dyhrman, 2016; Sigmund et al., 2017).

Various studies have highlighted the benefits of microalgae-based agricultural products owing to their diverse composition, which includes carbohydrates, pigments, lipids, proteins, minerals, and vitamins (Strauch and do Nascimento, 2021). Furthermore, microalgal biomass positively affects plant cultivation (Coppens et al., 2016; Garcia-Gonzalez and Sommerfeld, 2016; Barone et al., 2017; Dagnaisser et al., 2022) and several studies have demonstrated their effectiveness as fertilisers, specifically driving improved seed germination, root development, nutrient uptake, and reduced abiotic stress, which collectively increase crop efficiency (Bhalamurugan et al., 2018; Bello et al., 2021; Dagnaisser et al., 2022). Nagarajan et al. (2020) suggested that harnessing the nutrients recovered by microalgae from natural environments could offer a viable solution to addressing the globally growing fertiliser demand. However, the biochemical composition of microalgae varies based on species, culture environment, and other factors (Sharma, 2012; Madhubalaji et al., 2020). Therefore, despite intense research on the biotechnological potential of microalgae (Dolganyuk et al., 2020), comprehensive field-scale research is essential to address future challenges before their potential commercialisation as a biofertiliser (Renuka et al., 2018).

Toward this goal, we hypothesised that the incorporation of live microalgal biofertilisers improves the morphology, physiology, and development of cauliflower plants, leading to increased production and quality of cauliflower inflorescences. To test our hypothesis, we evaluated the effects of incorporating live microalgae in cauliflower crop fertilisation on plant morphology, yield, and head quality. This approach aligns with the principles of circular bioeconomy and sustainability, aiming to enhance the efficiency of cauliflower cultivation. Given the absence of prior research on the combined use of microalgae and inorganic fertilisers in cauliflower crops, we adopted an experimental design that sought to reveal whether incorporating microalgae in fertilisation influences cauliflower cultivation. The findings of this study will facilitate a broader discourse on sustainable practices in agriculture and food production.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study location and general experimental conditions

This study was conducted between August and November 2021. The site was located on a plot of land in Ventas de Zafarraya, Granada, Spain (36°57'29.2"N 4°06'48.2"W; 36.958111, -4.113394). The plot had a total area of 4389 m², of which 700 m² was used. According to the USDA classification, the soil in which the crop was grown had sandy loam texture; specifically, its components were as follows: clay (21.5 %), loam (34.9 %), and sand (43.6 %). The amount of oxidisable organic matter in the soil was 2.34 % on a dry matter basis. The pH of the soil sample was 8.2 with an extraction ratio of 1:2:5 H₂O, indicating alkalinity. The electrical conductivity (EC) of the saturated extract (1:5 H₂O) at 25 °C was 0.19 dS m⁻¹. The pH, EC at 25 °C, and nitrate concentration of irrigation water used in this study were 7.7, 0.662 dS m⁻¹, and 59 mg L⁻¹, respectively.

The average climate and environmental data for the study period are presented in Table 1. The climate data were obtained from the Zafarraya weather station, located in the province of Granada (latitude 36° 59' 25" N, longitude 04° 09' 13" W) at an altitude of 892 m above sea level. The Universal Transverse Mercator coordinates of the stations are X =

Table 1

Average environmental data for the study months in 2021.

	Temperature (°C)	RH (%)	Radiation (W/m ²)	Precipitation (mm)	ET ₀
August	22.97	60.84	6258.38	0.33	4.48
September	18.96	64.12	5402.82	0.53	3.38
October	14.69	70.22	4438.92	0.61	2.25
November	11.56	71.82	2661.32	2.96	1.52

RH: relative humidity; ET₀: reference evapotranspiration.

397,321 and Y = 4,094,420.

2.2. Vegetal material

The cauliflower variety 'Ferrara' was used in this study. This variety is characterised by its heat tolerance, which makes it ideal for cultivation in the study area for a growing cycle of spring, summer, and autumn. The growth cycle of 'Ferrara' is short, lasting approximately 70–85 days. The plants exhibit medium vigour and produce dense heads with a smooth texture and good commercial quality. Plants from the nursery were transplanted on 10/08/2021 with a planting density of 3.3 plants m⁻² in a planting frame size of 0.6 m × 0.5 m and the crop harvesting ended on 05/11/2021. The crop was drip irrigated at the rate of 2.2 L h⁻¹ using self-compensating, anti-drain drip emitters. The density of the drippers was 6 emitters/m⁻². The cultivation practices (transplanting, weeding, phytosanitary treatments, and harvesting) were performed per the local practices in the production area.

The solution of live microalgae comprised a mixture of species from the *Chlorophyceae* and *Trebouxiophyceae* classes. It included an initial mixture of *Chlorella* sp. (*Trebouxiophyceae*) and *Scenedesmus* sp. (*Chlorophyceae*) in a 1:1 ratio. The live microalgae were cultivated using the G2G® culture technology (Seville, Spain). The properties of the microalgal solution used in this study are listed in Table 2.

Table 2

Properties of the microalgae solution used in this study.

Characteristics	Values	Characteristics	Values
pH	6.5	Dissolved phosphorus	100.000 mg L ⁻¹
Electrical conductivity at 25 °C	3.92 dS m ⁻¹	Dissolved iron	2.90 mg L ⁻¹
Sodium absorption ratio (S.A.R.)	2.52	Dissolved manganese	2.50 mg L ⁻¹
Hardness	17.7 (°French)	Dissolved zinc	3.30 mg L ⁻¹
Scott index	3.50 mg L ⁻¹	Dissolved boron	2.20 mg L ⁻¹
Carbonates (CaCO ₃)	<0.06 (meq L)	Sum of anions	23.0 (meq L ⁻¹)
Bicarbonates (HCO ₃ ⁻)	2.04 (meq L ⁻¹)	Sum of cations	20.9 (meq L ⁻¹)
Sulfates (SO ₄ ²⁻)	0.7120 (meq L ⁻¹)	Osmotic pressure	1.410 (atm)
Chlorides (Cl ⁻)	16.600 (meq L ⁻¹)	Langelier index	-1.50
Nitrates (NO ₃ ⁻)	3.7100 (meq L ⁻¹)	Ryznar index	9.2
Fluorides (F ⁻)	0.0630 (meq L ⁻¹)	Residual sodium carbonate	-1.49 (meq L ⁻¹)
Dissolved sodium	3.340 (meq L ⁻¹)	Total alkalinity	92.4 mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹
Dissolved potassium	14.1000 (meq)	Calcium hardness	111 mg CaO ₃ L ⁻¹
Dissolved calcium	2.220 (meq L ⁻¹)	Dissolved copper	1.200 mg L ⁻¹
Dissolved magnesium	1.3100 (meq L ⁻¹)		

2.3. Experimental design

As no prior information was available on the optimal dose and effects of the combination of microalgae with inorganic fertilisers in cauliflower cultivation, first, we evaluated the fertilising effects of microalgae on cauliflower crop yield and elucidated the interactions with inorganic fertilisers commonly used in the production area.

The 2²-factorial design allows investigation of the individual effects (or main effects) of each factor and helps determine the interactions between them (Montgomery, 2017). Therefore, in this experiment, we employed a 2²-factorial design and included two factors (inorganic fertiliser and microalgae), each at two levels (high and low doses), and evaluated four treatment combinations: low-dose inorganic fertiliser and low-dose microalgae, high-dose inorganic fertiliser and low-dose microalgae, low-dose inorganic fertiliser and high-dose microalgae, and high-dose inorganic fertiliser and high-dose microalgae. Each treatment outcome was analysed in three random replicates to obtain a better estimate of the experimental error and a more accurate estimate of the effect of microalgae on cauliflower-crop fertilisation. Consequently, 12 elemental plots (4 combinations × 3 replicates) of 58.3 m² each were included in this experiment.

High doses of both inorganic fertilisers and microalgae correspond to the optimal recommended doses for cauliflower cultivation in the production area. Low doses of inorganic fertilisers and microalgae corresponded to 50 % of the high doses. This design allowed us to characterise the effects of increasing the dose of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae, as well as the interaction effect between factors when transitioning from low to optimal doses. The amounts of compounds in the high-dose inorganic fertilisation used in the study over the entire crop cycle period were 21 % ammonium sulphate + 60 % sulphur oxide (224 kg ha⁻¹), 54.5 % nitric acid (224 L ha⁻¹), 0–52 potassium sulphate (224 kg ha⁻¹), 13.7–0–46.3 potassium nitrate (224 kg ha⁻¹), and 13–40–13 N-P-K complex (224 kg ha⁻¹). The highest average dose of microalgal preparation considered for the entire crop cycle was 50 % *Chlorella* sp. + 50 % *Scenedesmus* sp. The total concentration of fresh microalgae was 25 g L⁻¹. Considering that the low dose was 50 % of the high dose, the total high-dose microalgal preparation applied to the crop was 448 L ha⁻¹ (16 L ha⁻¹ was applied with each irrigation).

The first irrigation was carried out on the day of transplantation, and the second irrigation was done 7 days after transplantation (DAT) using only water (48 and 12 L m⁻², respectively). Intense watering followed by dry periods of seven days at the beginning of the crop cycle is a common practice in the production area, with the aim of inducing greater root development during the initial crop phase. Starting 14 DAT, fertigation using water combined with corresponding inorganic fertiliser + microalgae doses was performed in all subsequent irrigations. The fertigation period varied depending on the phenological state of the crop: the "seedling" phase (14–48 DAT; 34 days), the "medium-sized plant" phase, which ended when head formation began (49–67 DAT; 18 days), and the final "until harvest" phase (68–84 DAT; 16 days). During the first phase, 3 L m⁻² of fertigation was performed every 2 days. In the second phase, fertigation was performed every 3 days at a dose of 6 L m⁻². In the last phase, fertigation was performed every 4 days at a dose of 9 L m⁻².

2.4. Data collection: plant morphology, production, performance components, and quality

Two days before harvesting, a subsample of 12 plants was randomly selected from each treatment combination (4 plants/replicate × 3 replicates/combination = 12 plants/combination), and the number of leaves, plant height from the ground, neck height, and plant diameter were measured. Plant height was measured using a graduated tape. The neck height and diameter were determined using digital callipers (measuring range of 0–150 mm, resolution of 0.01 mm). In addition, leaf samples were collected to perform sap analysis of the central leaf nerves,

following the procedure described by Esteves et al. (2021). Fragments of the central leaf nerve were collected to obtain the sap and a metal press equipped with a small-hole sieve was used to extract the sap. For the sap analysis, LAQUAtwin® portable metres were used and the pH, EC, nitrate, calcium, potassium, and sodium contents were estimated. These portable devices are efficient and cost-effective in obtaining results. They provide producers an opportunity to fine-tune fertilisation, ensuring not only proper plant nutrition but also contributing to improved environmental sustainability. The rapid diagnosis of nutrient concentrations plays a critical role in minimising the adverse effects associated with nutritional deficiencies, which, in turn, reduces their impact on crop production (Esteves et al., 2021).

On the day of harvest, crop yield, weight, and number of cauliflowers were determined. All the cauliflower curds produced in each elemental plot were individually weighed and counted. A BEC Engineering digital balance (METTLER TOLEDO® Balances, Greifensee, Switzerland), with a resolution of 1 g, was used for weighing. Plant morphology was evaluated for each of the randomly selected 12 cauliflower subsamples from the elemental plots, and the number of inflorescences (curds or florets) was individually counted.

2.5. Statistical analyses

The data were subjected to analysis of variance according to the 2² designs described in Eq. (1):

$$Y_{ijk} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + (\alpha\beta)_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ijk} \quad (1)$$

where Y_{ijk} is the ij -th observation, μ is the global mean, α_i is the effect of the i th level of inorganic fertiliser (high, low), β_j is the effect of the j -th level of microalgae (high, low), $(\alpha\beta)_{ij}$ is the effect of the interaction between the high and low levels of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae content on the fertiliser doses, and ε_{ijk} is the experimental error (Montgomery, 2017).

Significant interaction tends to mask the significance of the main effects (Freund et al., 2010). To help better interpret the effects associated with the main factors applied to the two levels (Factorial 2²), a one-way analysis of the variance was performed, corresponding to the combinations of the two microalgae levels plus the inorganic fertiliser (Eq. (2)). This analysis was performed only for the variables that showed significant interaction in the factor analysis.

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where Y_{ij} is the ij -th observation, μ is the global mean, α_i is the effect of the i th combined treatment of two highs (↑) and lows (↓) of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae (↑ Fertiliser + ↑ Microalgae, ↑ Fertiliser + ↓ Microalgae, ↓ Fertiliser + ↑ Microalgae, and ↓ Fertiliser + ↓ Microalgae), and ε_{ij} is the experimental error (Montgomery, 2017). The averages between the treatments showing significant differences in one-way ANOVA were compared using Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test, following the methodology described by Ciriello et al. (2023).

Statgraphics Centurion 19 software (version 19.5.01) was used for data analyses. The normality and homoscedasticity of the data were verified in all analyses.

3. Results

The factorial design revealed the effects associated with increasing doses of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae and their interactions. In addition, we observed an interaction when the increase in the inorganic fertiliser dose did not produce the same effect on the response variables associated with the increase in the microalgae dose. The combined effects of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae on plant morphology at the time of harvest, leaf sap nutrient content, and crop yield are described below.

3.1. Effects of microalgae fertilisation on plant morphology

Higher doses of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae resulted in higher plant height and leaf number, larger stem diameter, and lower stem slenderness than lower doses. However, no significant differences were found in stem length or the ratio of plant height to stem height as a percentage. The interaction between inorganic fertiliser and microalgae was significant only for plant height (Table 3).

The plant height increased by 4 cm as the inorganic fertiliser dose increased. The height increased further (8 cm) with increased microalgal dose. These findings provide evidence that combining inorganic fertiliser with microalgae significantly increases plant height compared with the effect observed when the fertiliser or microalgae are used alone. The number of plant leaves also showed a significant increase with high doses of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae, resulting in increases of 2 and 3 leaves per plant, respectively. The average stem diameter increased at high doses and differed significantly between the inorganic fertiliser (0.53 cm) and microalgae (0.48 cm). Stem slenderness was significantly lower at higher doses of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae than that at lower doses. Additionally, the stem-to-plant height ratio differed significantly only between the microalgae doses, with the ratio being higher at the lower dose. Increasing microalgal doses reduced the stem-to-plant height ratio by 1.6 %.

Next, we performed a simple analysis of variance for plant height, which showed a significant interaction between microalgae and inorganic fertiliser in the 2²-factor analysis (Table 3). A high dose of microalgae resulted in the maximum plant height, regardless of the dose of inorganic fertiliser it was combined with. Conversely, the low dose of inorganic fertiliser significantly improved plant height when combined with a high dose of microalgae, whereas the combination of low inorganic fertiliser and low microalgae resulted in lowest plant height (Fig. 1).

3.2. Effects of microalgae fertilisation on leaf sap nutrient content

Table 4 presents the results of the relationships between pH, EC, and nitrate, calcium, potassium, and sodium concentrations in the sap based on the inorganic fertiliser and microalgae levels at two different doses. The sap pH showed no significant differences with respect to the inorganic fertiliser and microalgae doses. The EC of the sap was significantly higher when the inorganic fertiliser dose was increased. Regarding the nitrate concentration in the sap, significant differences were observed when both the inorganic fertiliser and microalgae doses were increased. Furthermore, this increase in sap nitrate did not follow the same pattern of increasing the inorganic fertiliser dose as it did when increasing the microalgae dose, as evidenced by the significant interaction between these factors. The calcium, potassium, and sodium contents in the sap were also significantly influenced by the level of inorganic fertiliser and were higher at high doses than those at lower doses. Similarly, increasing the microalgae dose during crop nutrition increased the concentration of these nutrients in the sap.

Table 3

Morphological trait values of the cauliflower plant at harvest obtained using high and low levels of combined inorganic fertiliser and microalgae in crop nutrition.

	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves per plant	Stem diameter (cm)	Stem length (cm)	Stem slenderness	Stem/plant height (%)
Inorganic fertiliser						
High dose	80 ± 3.2	23 ± 1.9	5.96 ± 0.32	11.35 ± 1.24	1.91 ± 0.18	14.2 ± 1.6
Low dose	76 ± 5.2	21 ± 2.4	5.43 ± 0.33	11.33 ± 0.76	2.09 ± 0.19	14.9 ± 1.4
Significance	**	*	**	n.s.	*	n.s.
B: Microalgae						
High dose	82 ± 1.9	24 ± 1.7	5.93 ± 0.35	11.28 ± 1.27	1.90 ± 0.19	13.8 ± 1.5
Low dose	74 ± 3.5	21 ± 1.9	5.45 ± 0.33	11.40 ± 0.70	2.10 ± 0.17	15.4 ± 1.1
Significance	**	*	**	n.s.	*	*
A × B	*	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

The analysis of variance model: $Y_{ijk} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + (\alpha\beta) + \varepsilon_{ijk}$; n.s. (not significant); *, ** or *** $P \leq 0.05, 0.01, \text{ and } 0.001$, respectively. Data shown are mean values ± standard deviation ($n = 24$).

Fig. 1. Effects of microalgae (high, low) and fertiliser (high, low) interactions on plant height. Data represent means ± standard deviation ($n = 12$). Different letters above the bars indicate significant mean differences of each combination, assessed using Tukey's HSD test ($P < 0.001$) following the simple analysis of variance based on the $Y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$ model.

Next, we analysed the interaction effects of different combinations of inorganic fertilisers and microalgae doses on nitrate content in the sap of cauliflower leaves using unifactorial analysis. Combinations of high doses of inorganic fertiliser, regardless of the dose of microalgae as well as the low dose of fertiliser and high dose of microalgae, resulted in the highest nitrate content in the sap of cauliflower leaves. In contrast, the combination of the low dose of inorganic fertiliser and a low dose of microalgae resulted in the lowest concentration of nitrate in the sap (Fig. 2).

3.3. Effects of microalgae fertilisation on yield, weight, and the number of cauliflowers and curds

Considering that the planting density in our study was 3.3 plants m^{-2} , the number of commercially harvested cauliflowers, and thus the crop yield, was low. This low crop yield was also driven by root fungi and a high number of non-commercial (due to low quality) cauliflowers in some treatment combinations. The results of factor analysis for the combination of high and low levels of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae in terms of yield, weight, and number of cauliflower heads are listed in Table 5. High-dose inorganic fertilisation significantly increased yield (2.59 $t ha^{-1}$) and head weight (2.02 kg) compared to low-dose fertilisation (1.80 $t ha^{-1}$ and 1.78 kg ha^{-1} , respectively). In addition, the number of cauliflowers per ha and their head weights were lower in the low-dose inorganic fertiliser group than those in the high-dose fertiliser group. The microalgal dose also had a significant effect on the yield, number of cauliflowers per ha, and weight of the cauliflower heads. The high-dose microalgae resulted in a higher yield (2.38 $t ha^{-1}$) and head weight (1.98 kg) compared to the low-dose microalgae (2.01 $t ha^{-1}$ and 1.81 kg, respectively). The interaction between inorganic fertilisers and

Table 4

The pH, EC, nitrate, calcium, potassium, and sodium in the sap following the use of high and low levels of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae combinations.

	pH	EC	Nitrate (mg L ⁻¹)	Calcium (mg L ⁻¹)	Potassium (mg L ⁻¹)	Sodium (mg L ⁻¹)
A: Inorganic fertiliser						
High dose	7.0 ± 0.1	14.93 ± 1.04	5517 ± 726	1233 ± 150	4067 ± 393	156 ± 17
Low dose	6.9 ± 0.1	13.03 ± 1.40	4850 ± 917	807 ± 101	3483 ± 503	136 ± 19
Significance	n.s.	*	*	***	**	*
B: Microalgae						
High dose	6.9 ± 0.1	13.92 ± 1.47	5950 ± 607	1100 ± 214	4117 ± 354	157 ± 21
Low dose	7.0 ± 0.1	14.05 ± 1.46	4417 ± 908	940 ± 207	3433 ± 454	135 ± 15
Significance	n.s.	n.s.	***	*	**	*
A × B	n.s.	n.s.	**	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

EC: electrical conductivity.

The analysis of variance model: $Y_{ijk} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + (\alpha\beta) + \varepsilon_{ijk}$; n.s. (not significant); *, ** or *** $P \leq 0.05, 0.01, \text{ and } 0.001$, respectively. Data represent mean values ± standard deviation ($n = 24$).**Fig. 2.** Effects of microalgae (high, low) and fertiliser (high, low) interactions on nitrate content in the sap of cauliflower leaves. Data represent means ± standard deviation ($n = 12$). Different letters above the bars indicate significant mean differences of each combination, assessed using Tukey's HSD test ($P < 0.001$) following the simple analysis of variance based on the $Y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$ model.**Table 5**

Yield, weight, and number of heads and curds per head of cauliflower obtained using combinations of high- and low-dose inorganic fertiliser and microalgae.

	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Head weight (kg)	Number of cauliflowers per ha	Curds per head
A: Inorganic fertiliser				
High dose	2.59 ± 0.34	2.02 ± 0.17	12,819 ± 1064	21.0 ± 1.9
Low dose	1.80 ± 0.19	1.78 ± 0.15	10,168 ± 1095	18.1 ± 2.5
Significance	***	***	*	**
B: Microalgae				
High dose	2.38 ± 0.57	1.98 ± 0.21	11,980 ± 1853	20.2 ± 2.5
Low dose	2.00 ± 0.34	1.81 ± 0.10	11,056 ± 1644	18.9 ± 2.0
Significance	**	*	*	*
A × B	*	*	n.s.	n.s.

The analysis of variance model: $Y_{ijk} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + (\alpha\beta) + \varepsilon_{ijk}$; n.s. (not significant); *, ** or *** $P \leq 0.05, 0.01, \text{ and } 0.001$, respectively. Data represent mean values ± standard deviation ($n = 6$).

microalgae significantly influenced crop yield and head weight, indicating that the combination of inorganic fertilisation and microalgae does not follow a simple sum of individual effects in crop nutrition; rather, they modify each other synergistically.

To better understand the effects of our main factors applied at the two levels and their interactions on the yield and head weight (Table 5),

we performed a one-factor analysis of variance. The results identified the combination of high-dose inorganic fertiliser and high-dose microalgae as the most efficient combination for increased yield (2.88 t ha⁻¹; Fig. 3A) compared to the other combinations. Similarly, the combination of the high doses of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae also enhanced the average head weight compared to the remaining dose combinations (Fig. 3B).

4. Discussion

4.1. Plant morphology

Microalgal biomass, rich in amino acids beneficial to plants (Michalak and Chojnacka, 2015), acts as a biostimulant and promotes plant and root growth (Di Domenico Ziero et al., 2020). When applied as a biofertiliser, microalgal biomass releases bioactive substances (i.e., carbohydrates, proteins, enzymes, vitamins, and hormones), when promote plant growth and mitigate plant stress responses (Solomon et al., 2023). Garcia-Gonzalez and Sommerfeld (2016) demonstrated the positive effects of applying cell extracts and dry biomass of green algae (*Acutodesmus dimorphus*) as biofertilisers on tomato plants. A previous study reported similar effects of commercial organic fertiliser treatments and microalgae on the growth of tomato plants, whereas microalgae treatment improved the dry weight of the plants (Coppens et al., 2016). Similarly, El-Arroussi et al. (2018) found that the application of microalgal exopolysaccharides to tomato plants under salt stress improved their length and dry weight. In sugar beets, increased total and fine root lengths and the number of root tips were reported in microalgae-treated plants (Barone et al., 2017). The study suggested the biostimulatory effects of microalgal extracts on the root traits and expression of genes related to nutrient uptake in sugar beets (Barone et al., 2017). Consistent with these findings, our study showed that increasing doses of inorganic fertiliser or microalgae increased plant height, stem diameter, and leaf number in cauliflower plants. This improvement in plant growth and biomass is consistent with that described in tomatoes (Garcia-Gonzalez and Sommerfeld, 2016; Coppens et al., 2016; EL-Arroussi et al., 2018). The cauliflower stem grew only in diameter while maintaining its length, when treated with high doses of microalgae or fertiliser. A sturdier stem provides better structural support to the plant, allowing it to stand upright and better withstand adverse weather conditions such as strong wind or heavy rain. Furthermore, a robust stem can enhance the transport of water and nutrients from the roots to the upper parts of the plant, contributing to its growth. These findings corroborate those of a previous study demonstrating that fertilisation with microalgae biomass improves plant growth and root systems (Di Domenico Ziero et al., 2020).

We observed significant interaction effects of the inorganic fertiliser and microalgae on plant height, inferring that the combination of both the factors substantially changed plant height compared to the effects observed using inorganic fertiliser or microalgae alone. Further

Fig. 3. Effects of microalgae (high, low) and fertiliser (high, low) interactions on (A) yield and (B) cauliflower weight (B). Data represent means \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). Different letters above the bars indicate significant mean differences of each combination, assessed using Tukey's HSD test ($***P < 0.001$; $**P < 0.01$) following the simple analysis of variance based on the $Y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$ model.

analysis of the interaction effects demonstrated that low doses of microalgae significantly reduced the plant height compared to the high-dose microalgae combinations, with the lowest plant height being observed in the low-dose combination of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae. In contrast, Díaz-Pérez et al. (2023) demonstrated no significant differences in the leaf number or plant height of cauliflowers grown in agricultural soil to which various organic fertiliser treatments were applied along with microalgae, compost, livestock manure, and inorganic fertilisers with different proportions of N-P-K fertiliser units. However, considering that these authors used optimal fertilisation doses for the crop, our results partially align with those of Díaz-Pérez et al. (2023). In our study, the use of higher doses of microalgae combined with both high and low doses of inorganic fertiliser, analysed as independent treatments (\uparrow Microalgae + \uparrow Fertiliser and \uparrow Microalgae + \downarrow Fertiliser), did not reveal significant differences in cauliflower plant height, which coincides with the findings reported by Díaz-Pérez et al. (2023). Concordant with our study, Puglisi et al. (2020) demonstrated that inorganic fertiliser combined with a microalgal extract of *S. quadricauda* increased shoot growth and plant dry matter of lettuce. Together, our findings suggest that the number of leaves and plant height increase significantly with the combination of inorganic fertilisers with high doses of microalgae.

Water and fertilisation play crucial roles in shaping plant morphology, affecting roots, stems, leaves, and inflorescences (Wenneck et al., 2021). Under conditions of drought and nutrient scarcity, plants typically exhibit weaker stems (Kusvuran and Kusvuran, 2019). However, the use of microalgae-based fertilisers alleviates the effects of drought stress, improves nutrient absorption, increases the production of secondary metabolites, and strengthens plant antioxidant defence systems (Kusvuran, 2021). Stem diameter is a key factor determining the plant-bearing capacity, metabolite translocation, and crop yield of cauliflower (Teixeira et al., 2022). Variations in plant height, leaf diameter, and area are likely influenced by different fertiliser dose combinations, affecting meristem multiplication, and modifying the levels of endogenous gibberellins responsible for cell elongation (Mog et al., 2019; Prodhan et al., 2022). The observed variations in stem shape in the present study support these hypotheses. Significant differences were evident in stem diameter, particularly with high doses of both inorganic fertiliser and microalgae. However, the stem length remained constant across all treatments. This resulted in sturdier and less slender stems when the doses of inorganic fertiliser or microalgae were increased. The relationship between stem height and total plant height showed significant variations as a function of microalgae dose, being greater at lower doses. Our findings indicate that the combination of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae reduces the amount of inorganic fertiliser required without compromising the plant structure, morphology, and quality of cauliflower curd, which is consistent with

the findings of several other studies (García-González and Sommerfeld, 2016; Coppens et al., 2016; Díaz-Pérez et al., 2023).

4.2. Sap analysis

Nutrients present in the sap drive plant development (Esteves et al., 2021). Sap analysis is considered an alternative method for evaluating the nutritional status of plants, provides a real-time diagnosis (Incrocci et al., 2017; Thompson et al., 2017; Llanderal et al., 2019; Padilla et al., 2020). Petiole sap analysis is effective in diagnosing the nutritional status of tomatoes (Farneselli et al., 2014). In our study, the pH of cauliflower leaf sap remained consistent across varying doses of inorganic fertiliser and microalgae, while sap EC significantly increased only with an increase in the inorganic fertiliser dose. Calcium, potassium, and sodium contents in the sap significantly increased with elevated doses of both inorganic fertiliser and microalgae. However, no interactions were observed between these nutrients and the main factors.

Evaluation of nitrogen content in crops is essential for effective nitrogen management in intensive vegetable production (Peña-Fleitas et al., 2015). Petiole sap nitrate content is a highly sensitive indicator of plant nutritional status (Altamimi et al., 2013; Buoso et al., 2023). In our study, the nitrate content in the sap increased significantly at higher doses of both fertiliser and microalgae. This finding is consistent with the findings of Coppens et al. (2016), who found increased N in tomato leaves when microalgae was used as a fertiliser. Furthermore, in our study, a significant interaction was observed between inorganic fertilisers and microalgae in terms of nitrate concentration. This suggested that the increase in nitrate concentration did not follow the same trend when treated with increased inorganic fertiliser doses compared to the effects observed with microalgae doses. Analysing the effects of four combinations independently revealed that the effects of the combination of low doses of fertilisers and microalgae reduced the sap nitrate content compared to those of the other combinations, which showed similar sap nitrate content. Additionally, the low dose of inorganic fertiliser maximally increased sap nitrate content when combined with a high dose of microalgae. Therefore, the inorganic fertiliser dose can be reduced while maintaining an adequate level of sap nitrate, provided that the fertiliser is combined with an appropriate dose of microalgae.

4.3. Yield, weight, and number of cauliflowers

Microalgae contribute growth-promoting compounds, including nutrients and organic compounds, fostering plant development (Kapoor et al., 2021). In crops such as cauliflower, where inflorescences (or curds) are marketed and consumed, combining microalgae and fertiliser is a potentially suitable alternative to curtail inorganic fertiliser use (Álvarez-González et al., 2022). Microalgae in

biofertilisers contain high concentrations of nutrients such as N, P, Cu, Fe, Zn, and Na; thus, supplementing with microalgal biomass can immensely benefit crop cultivation (Ferreira et al., 2023). Specifically, these microalgae enhance crop growth and health by facilitating nitrogen fixation, releasing trace elements from the soil, solubilising potassium and phosphorus, producing exopolysaccharides, and converting organic matter into usable nutrients (Solomon et al., 2023). Many studies on crops like cauliflowers have corroborated this claim (Ronga et al., 2019; Kang et al., 2021). Sharma et al. (2021) compared the efficiency of *Chlorella* biomass-based biofertiliser and an equivalent dose of an inorganic NPK fertiliser in spinach and found that microalgal biomass improved spinach yield. Puglisi et al. (2020) demonstrated that a foliar application of *Scenedesmus quadricauda* extract on lettuce seedlings improved their growth. Dineshkumar et al. (2020) demonstrated that a mixture of two marine microalgae improved the yield of onion crops. Furthermore, Díaz-Pérez et al. (2023) demonstrated that combining microalgae and compost in cauliflower cultivation generated yields comparable to those obtained using chemical fertilisers.

We observed a synergistic interaction between inorganic fertiliser and microalgae in context of cauliflower head yield and weight. The highest yield resulted from the combination of high doses of microalgae and inorganic fertiliser, while the other combinations did not show significant effects. Similarly, the combination of high doses of fertilisers and microalgae resulted in a significantly higher head weight than those observed in the other combinations.

Concordant with the previous studies (Kholssi et al., 2019; Puglisi et al., 2020; Dineshkumar et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2021; Díaz-Pérez et al., 2023), our study suggests that combining inorganic fertilisers and microalgae offers a sustainable approach for reducing inorganic fertiliser usage without affecting the yield and quality of cauliflower. This congruence validates the high nutritional value of microalgal biomass in the context of crop cultivation (Alvarenga et al., 2023). Nevertheless, further studies are essential to unveil the optimal combination of inorganic fertilisers and microalgae, which can maximise the yield, weight, and number of cauliflower heads.

4.4. Limitations and future research

The potential limitations of the present study include the impact of environmental factors during the research, lack of analysis of long-term effects, and a deficiency in an in-depth economic analysis. Consequently, it is crucial to conduct further investigations into the use of these microalgae over years and undertake economic studies to scrutinise the long-term environmental and economic effects.

5. Conclusions

The study demonstrates that the combination of inorganic fertilisers and microalgae significantly influences cauliflower plant growth characteristics, sap nutrient content, and overall yield. Higher doses of inorganic fertilisers or microalgae positively impact plant height, stem diameter, leaf number, and nutrient levels in cauliflower leaves, which translates to an improved yield, larger cauliflower heads, and more curds per head. Our findings confirm that combined use of microalgae with inorganic fertilisers enhances cauliflower cultivation, and thus, offers a sustainable alternative with reduced reliance on inorganic fertilisers without compromising crop yield and quality. Further studies should focus on determining the optimal microalgae dosage to minimise inorganic fertiliser usage while maximising cauliflower crop productivity and quality.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Manuel Díaz-Pérez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Juan Manuel Moreno Moreno:** Validation,

Investigation. **José Javier Hernández García:** Validation, Investigation. **Ángel-Jesús Callejón-Ferre:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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